

Supplementary Information

Catalytic Resource Recovery for Transformation of Wastewater Industry

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Supplementary Note 1: Course of resource recovery in water treatment

Wastewater resource utilisation dates to ancient civilisations, where wastewater was repurposed for agricultural irrigation. By the mid-19th century, industrialisation led to severe water pollution, prompting the development of sewage systems focusing solely on pollutant removal. In the early 20th century, the value of wastewater components gained recognition, as exemplified by using sewage sludge for agriculture or biogas production. A significant shift then occurred in the mid-20th century due to global environmental crises (e.g., Minamata Disease, London smog) and the rise of circular economy concepts. In this period, water treatment goals were transformed from mere pollutant removal to sustainable resource recovery. By the late 20th century, innovations in biological (e.g., activated sludge, biofilm processes, and anaerobic digestion) and physicochemical technologies (e.g., chemical precipitation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, and advanced oxidation processes) laid the technical foundation for broadening wastewater reuse.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, a significant progress in wastewater recycling has been driven by the following key factors: i) **Policy support at global and national levels:** The adoption of Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6) - “Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all” - by the United Nations in 2015, alongside the establishment of carbon neutrality and reduction targets by various countries since 2019, has created strong policy incentives for wastewater recycling. ii) **Technological innovations:** The integration of nanomaterials, advanced manufacturing, and artificial intelligence into wastewater treatment has enabled intelligent, efficient, and highly optimised resource recovery processes. iii) **Economic incentives:** Resource shortages and energy crises have repositioned wastewater as a valuable resource, containing recoverable materials such as noble metals, heavy metals, and hydrocarbon byproducts. Resource recovery not only reduces disposal costs but also generates significant economic returns. iv) **Industry demonstration and practice:** Trade associations and standardisation organisations have established technical guidelines for wastewater recycling, fostering technological advancements and industry-wide transformation. Notable achievements in energy self-sufficient sewage treatment plants and zero-liquid discharge systems exemplify the successful industrial deployment of advanced wastewater recycling solutions.

Therefore, wastewater resource recovery has evolved into a profitable, sustainable, and technologically sophisticated pathway, addressing both environmental challenges and economic demands in a new era.

Supplementary Note 2. Estimated based on empirical values

Estimated based on empirical values refers to values derived from average market prices, reported product yields, and cost-performance ratios obtained from prior literature and industrial reports. Unless otherwise specified:

i). Market prices were sourced from recent industrial commodity databases (e.g., ICIS, Alibaba, Metal Markets). When product purity was not specified, the lowest available price for industrial-grade materials was applied;

ii). Pollutant removal efficiencies were estimated based on bench-scale or pilot-scale experiments using comparable wastewater matrices, as reported in peer-reviewed studies;

iii). Product yields (e.g., recovery rates of Au, Cu, or polymerised products) were determined from established reaction stoichiometries or the average experimental values reported in at least two independent references;

iv). Process costs include estimated expenditures for electricity, chemical reagents, and operation and maintenance, normalised by the mass of the target pollutant and assuming standard conditions (25 °C, neutral pH unless otherwise noted);

v). Incomes were calculated by multiplying the product yield by its estimated unit market price.

Supplementary Figure 1. Industrial wastewater and its component recycle.

Supplementary Table 1. Representative examples of CRRT from various wastewaters.

Industries	Pollutant	Catalytic mode	Catalyst	Product	Ref.	
Metallurgy	Au(III)	Reduction	Pyrocarbon	Au(0)	S1	
	Pd(II)		PAF	Pd(0)	S2	
	Ag(I)		MoO _x	Ag(0)	S3	
	Sb(III)	Electrocatalysis	Pd/carbon	Sb(0)	S4	
Electroplating	Cr(VI)	Reduction	Amine polymers	Cr(III)	S5	
	Ni(II)-EDTA	Electrocatalysis	PbO ₂ and Ti	Ni(0)	S6	
	Cu(II)-EDTA	Reduction	Cu	Cu, EDTA	S7	
Stock farming	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	Electrocatalysis	KNiHCF	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ , KOH, H ₂ O ₂ ,	S8	
Manufacturing	NO ₃ ⁻ -N		Cu-Ni	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	S9	
			Ni(OH) ₂ @Ni		S10	
	Chlorophenols		Rh NPs-PdMER	Cyclohexanol	S11	
			Ru		S12	
	Anilines		Polymerisation	CuO	Polyaniline	S13
	Phenols			Heat	Polyphenols	S14
				Co ₃ O ₄		S15
				MOX		S16
	Thiophenes			CuO	Polythiophenes	S17
Sulfamethoxazole	N-doped CNT	Oligomers		S18		
	Fe-N ₄ SACs			S19		

Supplementary Table 2. Characteristics of wastewater from different industries and traditional recycling technologies.

Industries	Major Pollutants	Associated Pollutants	pH	Recovery Strategies & Technologies
Metallurgy, Electroplating & Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy metal ions • Acids or alkalis • Suspended solids • Cyanides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chelating agents • Beneficiation reagents • Residual coagulants • Inorganic salts • Rare-earth metals 	<2 or >10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precipitation, ion exchange, electrodeposition, and extraction methods to reclaim heavy metals and rare elements; • Membrane technology to recycle tailings water and collect heavy metal precipitations used as metallurgical raw materials.
Chemical & Fine Chemical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recalcitrant organics • High-COD organics • Acids or alkalis • Solvent residues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By-products • Unreacted substrates • Metal catalysts • Salts and inorganic ions 	2–11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extraction, distillation, membrane separation, and adsorption to recover valuable organic solvents, precious metals, and inorganic salts.
Petroleum Refining & Petrochemical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oils • Phenols • Toxic inorganic species • Suspended solids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Halogenated organics • Heterocyclic compounds • Surfactants • Trace metals 	6–9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flotation and membrane technologies to extract oils and hydrocarbons for reuse as a fuel or feedstock. • Evaporation and crystallization to recover inorganics as industrial salt or as a petrochemical auxiliary raw material.
Pharmaceutical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active pharmaceutical ingredients and intermediates • Organic solvents • High-salinity nutrients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unreacted raw materials • Toxic by-products • Additives • Disinfection by-products 	5–9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extraction, membrane separation, crystallization, and adsorption to recover valuable drug intermediates; • Distillation to recover organic solvents and inorganic salts.
Pulp & Paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cellulose • Hemicellulose • Lignin and derivatives • Chlorinated organics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bleaching by-products • Residual additives • Surfactants • Microbial metabolites • Trace metals 	10–11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alkali recovery system (e.g. evaporation, incineration, causticising process) to recover black liquor; • Precipitation and filtration to recover paper fibers and fillers; • Membrane separation or specific enzymatic hydrolysis process to obtain raw materials of aromatic compounds.
Food & Beverage Processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic nutrients (fats, proteins, carbohydrates) • Suspended solids • Nitrogen • Phosphorus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disinfectant residues • Surfactants • Food additives • Microbial metabolites • Inorganic salts 	4–8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, and fermentation to recover valuable components (e.g., proteins, pectin); • Anaerobic digestion to generate biogas and extract fermentation by-products for feed or food additives.

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